

Insomnia and Emotion Regulation: A Narrative Review of Empirical Findings and Underlying Mechanisms

Nespavost a Emoční Regulace: Narativní Přehled Empirických Poznatků a Podkladových Mechanismů

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Summary:

Insomnia is the most common sleep disorder and a prevalent mental health issue, characterised by challenges in initiating or maintaining sleep, which negatively impacts daytime functioning and overall quality of life. Insomnia is closely linked to emotion regulation (ER) and plays a significant role in its persistence. This literature review synthesises findings from 17 studies that show a consistent deficit in ER among people living with insomnia, highlighting issues like heightened hyperarousal, increased cognitive arousal before sleep, and reliance on maladaptive cognitive processes like self-blame, catastrophising and rumination. Evidence also indicates a bidirectional relationship between sleep and mood, with negative emotional reactivity emerging as a central mediator. Neurobiological research points to dysregulation within the prefrontal–limbic network and suggests that strengthening cingulo–limbic connectivity may benefit both sleep and mood. Standard interventions can alleviate insomnia symptoms and enhance ER, while approaches directly targeting ER strategies may offer individualised advantages. Treatment outcomes are further influenced by factors such as psychiatric comorbidity and coping styles. However, current research is limited by inadequate study designs and measurement inconsistencies. Future studies should adopt more rigorous and standardised methods to clarify mechanisms and improve treatment strategies for insomnia.

Keywords: Insomnia, emotion regulation, hyperarousal, cognitive behavioural therapy for insomnia, CBT-I

Souhrn (CZ):

Nespavost je nejčastější porucha spánku a závažný psychický problém, charakterizovaný obtížemi při usínání nebo udržení spánku, které negativně ovlivňují jak denní fungování, tak celkovou kvalitu života. Nespavost úzce souvisí s emoční regulací (ER) a hraje významnou roli v jejím přetrvávání. Tato přehledová studie shrnuje poznatky ze 17 studií, které konzistentně poukazují na deficity v ER u osob trpících nespavostí, přičemž zdůrazňují obtíže, jako je zvýšená vzrušivost, kognitivní aktivace před spánkem a spoléhání na maladaptivní kognitivní procesy, například sebeobviňování, katastrofizaci či ruminaci. Mezi spánkem a náladou existuje obousměrný vztah, přičemž negativní emoční reaktivita se ukazuje jako klíčový mediátor. Neurobiologické studie poukazují na dysregulaci v prefrontálně–limbickém okruhu a naznačují, že posílení cingulo–limbické konektivity by mohlo přispět ke zlepšení jak spánku, tak nálady. Standardní intervence mohou zmírnit příznaky nespavosti a podpořit účinnější regulaci emocí, zatímco přístupy zaměřené přímo na strategie ER mohou přinést individualizované benefity. Účinnost léčby však může být ovlivněna i dalšími faktory, například psychiatrickou komorbiditou nebo používanými copingovými strategiemi. Současný výzkum je však omezen nedostatečnými výzkumnými designy a nekonzistencí v měření. Budoucí výzkum by měl využívat rigoróznější a standardizované metodologie s cílem objasnit mechanismy a zlepšit strategie léčby nespavosti.

Klíčová slova: nespavost, emoční regulace, hyperarousal, kognitivně behaviorální terapie nespavosti, KBT-I

1. Introduction

Insomnia ranks as the most prevalent sleep disorder and the second most commonly cited mental health issue overall (1). It is a serious health concern, with about 24–35% of adults experiencing occasional insomnia and 9–15% dealing with chronic insomnia (2). In Europe, roughly 10% of the adult population meets the criteria for insomnia (3). This condition is characterised by difficulties related to falling asleep, sustaining sleep, and waking up too early (4). Such problems can have a substantial effect on daytime functioning and result in a notable decline in quality of life, along with heightened mental health risks (4). Additionally, insomnia frequently coexists with various health issues, including hypertension, chronic pain, or cancer (5). It is also recognised as an independent risk factor for the development of psychiatric disorders, particularly depression, anxiety, and substance abuse (6).

The mechanisms underlying insomnia are primarily explained through the hyperarousal model, which outlines a state of increased physiological and psychological engagement, marked by elevated levels of alertness and vigilance (7). This heightened state can impact both the autonomic and central nervous systems, in addition to influencing behaviour, cognition, and emotions throughout the day, ultimately leading to poorer sleep quality and adverse daytime effects, such as mood disturbances and reduced emotion regulation (ER), which may further elevate the risk of developing other mental disorders (7).

Recent research suggests that challenges in ER may be pivotal in the onset of insomnia (8). Studies indicate that insomnia is more closely linked to anxiety disorders than to negative sleep features alone (9). Neuroimaging studies have identified structural and functional alterations in the brain that are observable in both insomnia and depressive disorders, emphasising the common overlap between these conditions (10). A recent review examining brain mechanisms related to insomnia suggests that a tendency to develop insomnia may arise from neural circuits responsible for regulating emotion and arousal rather than those governing circadian rhythms and homeostatic sleep control (11).

In clinical settings, individuals experiencing insomnia frequently report challenges in ER (12). These challenges may encompass insufficient emotional processing, limited access to effective ER techniques, and a tendency to rely on maladaptive strategies such as worrying or ruminating (12). It is also possible that shortcomings in emotional memory processing, a key aspect of anxiety disorders, are pertinent to insomnia (13).

Considering the information outlined above, evidence suggests that ER difficulties are central to the onset and persistence of insomnia. Individuals with insomnia often struggle with maladaptive ER strategies, which intensify hyperarousal, impair emotional processing, and worsen daytime functioning. These difficulties not only contribute to the maintenance of poor sleep but also heighten vulnerability to psychiatric comorbidities. Subsequently, it is essential to investigate the role of ER to provide critical insights into shared neural and psychological mechanisms, which could highlight potential targets for more effective, integrative treatment approaches. Therefore, this review aims to synthesise the empirical evidence on ER deficits in individuals with insomnia, discuss underlying mechanisms, and explore potential clinical interventions.

2. Methodology

The literature search was carried out using two databases – PubMed and PsycINFO. Study selection of the current review included cross-sectional studies to identify and characterise ER deficits in adults with insomnia, providing the foundational evidence for what specific deficits exist. Longitudinal and prospective studies were included to clarify the temporal relationships and underlying mechanisms between insomnia and emotion dysregulation, helping to determine whether poor ER predisposes individuals to insomnia or if chronic sleep disturbance impairs emotional processing over time. Randomised controlled trials (RCTs) were included to evaluate clinical interventions targeting insomnia and ER, providing evidence-based treatment recommendations. Additionally, existing systematic reviews and meta-analyses served as foundational sources to contextualise findings and identify key primary studies, while ensuring comprehensive coverage of the literature. This multi-method approach allowed for a thorough examination of the empirical evidence across all three stated objectives:

synthesising knowledge about ER deficits, discussing underlying mechanisms, and evaluating clinical interventions for adults with insomnia

In our search, two groups of terms were used separately: a) ("*chronic insomnia*" OR "*insomnia disorder*" OR "*insomnia*") AND ("*emotion regulation*" OR "*emotional regulation*" OR "*emotion dysregulation*") AND ("*adult*" OR "*adults*") for PubMed and b) (*exp Insomnia/ or insomnia.mp.*) and (*exp Emotion Regulation/ or (emotion dysregulation or emotional regulation or emotion regulation).mp.*) and (*exp Adulthood/ or adult*.mp.*) for PsycINFO respectively.

We excluded any record that failed to meet all of the following criteria: (i) publication date 2015 – 2025; (ii) peer-reviewed empirical study involving human adults (≥ 18 y); (iii) assessment or experimental manipulation of both chronic insomnia and emotion-regulation (ER) constructs within the same sample; (iv) English-language full text; (v) insomnia constituted the primary study variable—that is, participants were recruited for insomnia or insomnia was the main predictor/outcome, not a secondary symptom of another disorder; (vi) use of validated instruments, interventions or tasks for both domains. Studies focusing on paediatric samples, mixed-age cohorts without adult-specific analyses, “sleep disturbance” in medical or psychiatric comorbidities (e.g., cancer-related sleep loss, PTSD insomnia) or relying on ad-hoc, single-item sleep/ER questions were excluded.

3. Results

3.1. Emotion-regulation disturbances observed in insomnia

As previously mentioned, the hyperarousal theory suggests that insomnia is accompanied by heightened emotional reactivity and emotional dysregulation. Therefore, we first examined studies that quantified ER capacity and baseline affect in adults with insomnia to establish whether a trait-level deficit exists. We have identified six studies investigating this phenomenon (14, 16 - 20).

Firstly, Palagini et al. conducted a cross-sectional, case-control study to test whether emotion-dysregulation mediates the link between resilience and hyperarousal (14). They recruited 56 adults meeting the criteria for insomnia disorder in accordance with the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders 5 (DSM-5; 15), who were compared to 38 matched good-sleeping controls at a single time-point with no experimental manipulation or longitudinal follow-up. Their findings show that insomnia patients reported significantly higher ER scores, trait sleep reactivity, and pre-sleep cognitive arousal. They also showed significantly lower resilience scores than the control group, which were negatively correlated with DERS scores. Additionally, further mediation analyses indicate that ER mediates the pathway from low resilience to increased hyperarousal. This suggests that low resilience feeds the hyperarousal cycle mainly through poor ER, further exacerbating insomnia difficulties.

Secondly, Garrivet et al. explored whether specific facets of ER and reactivity differ between insomnia alone in contrast with a comorbid major depressive episode (MDE; 16). Their observational, cross-sectional study, investigating 57 adults (27 insomnia + MDE patients; 30 standalone insomnia patients), showed that adults with a combination of chronic insomnia and MDE demonstrated comparable degrees of insomnia severity to those with standalone chronic insomnia. However, they displayed a sharply dysregulated emotional profile, being approximately one and a half times more likely to lean on maladaptive coping strategies such as self-blame and catastrophising, suggesting that self-directed negativity fuels the comorbidity. Behaviourally, participants with the comorbidity indicated dampened motivation and motor drive, consistent with psychomotor inhibition of depression. Moreover, emotional intensity and lability were found to be shared features of insomnia irrespective of mood status, suggesting that the baseline ER vulnerability is qualitatively amplified rather than initiated by the comorbidity. These findings indicate that comorbid MDE shifts insomnia from a state of oscillating, high-intensity emotions to one dominated by negative self-appraisal and behavioural shut-down.

Additionally, in a study conducted by Zhao et al., two large cross-sectional samples of students were analysed: a discovery arm with 917 participants and a replication arm with 652 participants (17). The researchers performed network and regression analyses to explore how insomnia severity relates to traits relevant to ER. The results indicated that hyperarousal was central to the network connecting insomnia with dysfunctional sleep beliefs, stress-reactive insomnia, depression, and fatigue. These variables collectively accounted for approximately 41–43% of the variance in insomnia scores. The

direct predictors of insomnia severity included dysfunctional beliefs, stress-reactive insomnia, physical fatigue, hyperarousal, and depression. Among these, hyperarousal showed the strongest correlations with private self-consciousness, dysfunctional beliefs, insomnia severity, and perfectionistic doubts and personal standards. The analysis of hub centrality revealed that trait anxiety, depressive rumination, perfectionism, and hyperarousal played significant roles in the network. Overall, these findings suggest a dysregulation framework at the trait level, where hyperarousal and maladaptive cognitions, such as dysfunctional beliefs, perfectionistic self-focus, and rumination, link insomnia to negative emotional states.

Furthermore, Cheng et al. examined the relationship between cognitive strategies and sleep quality among middle-aged and elderly adults (18). Their cross-sectional study among 653 Chinese participants was to explore how maladaptive cognitive emotional regulation strategies, such as catastrophising, rumination and self-blame, mediate the association between psychological resilience and insomnia severity. Outcomes in terms of cognitive ER strategies were derived primarily from the Cognitive Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (CERQ) and its nine subscales. The mediation analyses identified catastrophising as the dominant statistical driver of insomnia and the main conduit through which low resilience impairs sleep, whereas planning and reappraisal exerted protective effects. Overall, the maladaptive cognitive regulation strategies mediated approximately 13% of the resilience-insomnia pathway, suggesting that low-resilience individuals slept worse primarily because of the tendency to incline towards catastrophic or ruminative thinking. However, according to the results, the adaptive ER strategies, though beneficial in direct models, did not mediate insomnia, suggesting that boosting resilience alone is insufficient unless maladaptive cognition is simultaneously corrected.

Moreover, these findings were preceded by those of Palagini et al, who explored whether insomnia-specific daytime rumination is directly associated with trait hyperarousal, pre-sleep state arousal, global emotion dysregulation and whether the rumination mediates any of those arousal or dysregulation dimensions (19). Similarly to their aforementioned study regarding resilience, their cross-sectional, case-control study, investigating 67 subjects with insomnia disorder (diagnosed per DSM-5 criteria) and 36 good sleepers, presented participants with several measures assessing insomnia, arousal, insomnia-specific rumination and emotion dysregulation. According to their findings, insomnia-specific rumination was crucial in integrating trait and state hyperarousal with emotion dysregulation, exerting both direct and mediated effects, specifically in the insomnia group. Therefore, Palagini et al. hypothesise that the perseverative sleep-related cognitive processes contribute to insomnia perpetuation, connecting trait vulnerability, arousal and difficulties regulating emotions.

Lastly, one cross-sectional observational study investigated the role of insomnia-specific rumination further by exploring whether executive function deficits, such as cognitive inhibition and set-shifting, influence the rumination about daytime consequences of insomnia beyond two traditional predictors of the phenomenon - depressive symptoms and poor ER (20). Balleisio et al. have recruited 30 young adults diagnosed with insomnia disorder by clinical psychologists in accordance with the DSM-5 diagnostic criteria. They were presented with measures of insomnia, depression, ER and rumination about the daytime consequences of insomnia. Additionally, their executive functions were assessed by a task-switching paradigm. Their findings show that a combination of high depression and cognitive reappraisal, along with weak cognitive inhibition, significantly predicted increased rumination tendency. However, set-shifting showed no association with the extent of insomnia-specific rumination, implying that an inability to suppress intrusive thoughts, rather than difficulty switching tasks, sustains perseverative insomnia cognitions.

These studies show that adults with insomnia struggle to regulate emotions, experiencing heightened hyperarousal and cognitive arousal before sleep. They face greater emotional regulation difficulties and often rely on maladaptive thought patterns like dysfunctional beliefs about sleep, catastrophizing, and self-blame. Insomnia-related rumination links low resilience to increased arousal levels. Network analyses indicate that hyperarousal connects insomnia with depression and fatigue. Comorbid major depressive episodes lead to increased self-directed negativity and decreased behavioural activity. Additionally, poor cognitive inhibition, rather than the ability to shift attention, contributes to persistent negative thoughts about insomnia.

3.2. Dynamic, within-person sleep–emotion interplay

Having established and discussed a trait-level ER vulnerability in insomnia, we have also identified two studies (21, 22) that explore how these processes unfold from night to night. Therefore, the current section aims to review two micro-longitudinal studies that repeatedly track sleep and next-day affect/reactivity using various methods, such as sleep diaries and actigraphy.

Firstly, one micro-longitudinal study aimed to assess the connection between sleep characteristics, emotional processes, and depressive symptoms in people experiencing insomnia through a two-week daily longitudinal study, utilising sleep diaries and actigraphy to measure sleep (21). Their findings, gathered from 60 subjects with clinically significant insomnia, indicate that sleep quality and depressive symptoms are reciprocally predictive of each other at the daily level, especially when participants also reported heightened negative emotional reactivity, suggesting that higher depressive symptomatology led to lower sleep quality. The negative emotional reactivity also partially mediated the sleep efficiency (SE) effects at the between-subject level only, whereas positive reactivity and four common ER strategies (reappraisal, problem-solving, rumination, suppression) played no mediating role. These findings show that day-to-day spikes in negative emotional reactivity are the proximal mechanism linking sleep quality/efficiency to depressive symptoms, with mediation observed mainly at the within-individual level.

Secondly, Wassing et al. tested whether insomnia disorder impairs sleep-dependent downregulation and overnight adaptation of emotional distress (22). They recruited 64 participants (42 normal sleepers and 22 individuals with insomnia). They experimented within a between-group comparison across three days, where participants were exposed to an embarrassing stimulus at four different time points. When the distressing event was followed by sleep, results indicate that normal sleepers showed the expected overnight reduction in distress, especially in the physical and emotional domains. However, the individuals with insomnia disorder showed the opposite trend - sleep amplified the next-day physical distress relative to wake time, with no benefit for emotional or social distress, suggesting that people suffering from insomnia experience an adverse effect on adaptation if they sleep immediately after having been exposed to a self-conscious emotional experience. These findings indicate that insomnia inverts the sleep-dependent adaptive processes and worsens the next day's outcomes, with maladaptive sleep exacerbating the somatic distress signal rather than alleviating it.

In two studies, researchers found a bidirectional relationship between sleep quality and mood in individuals with insomnia. Poor sleep predicts higher depressive symptoms the next day and vice versa. Negative emotional spikes, rather than coping strategies, drive these daily connections. Additionally, insomnia can distort emotional experiences; for instance, after an embarrassing event, people living with insomnia reported increased distress the next day, unlike good sleepers who showed a decrease. These findings highlight the need to address negative emotional reactivity before bedtime in treatment.

3.3. Mechanistic and experimental insights

3.3.1. Neurobiological markers of ER-insomnia coupling

The following subsection builds on previous trait and cognitive-behavioural research findings to examine circuit-level evidence linking ER to insomnia. We review two studies that utilise functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and electroencephalography (EEG) to assess connectivity among the prefrontal cortex, limbic system, and the cingulo-thalamo-amygdalar pathways at rest (23, 24). These data aim to determine whether insomnia indicates a disruption in ER-related neural networks (as opposed to general hyperarousal), whether these markers correspond to symptoms, and whether they change with intervention.

Firstly, a randomised, single-blind, controlled clinical trial explored whether acupuncture modulates the emotional network resting-state functional connectivity (EN rsFC), specifically the amygdala, thalamus, anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and the hippocampus and whether such changes relate to sleep quality and affect (anxiety/depression), given evidence that insomnia and negative emotion share network dysregulation (23). They have recruited 90 participants (30 healthy controls and 60 individuals with insomnia disorder, randomised 1:1 into either real or sham conditions). However, after accounting for dropout, 26 participants in the real condition and 24 in the sham condition completed the study. At baseline, data indicate that the insomnia disorder group exhibited a

hyperconnected thalamic-limbic and ACC-prefrontal links at baseline versus the healthy control group, consistent with hyperarousal/emotional network dysregulation. The functional magnetic resonance imaging results show that four weeks of real acupuncture produced selective emotional network shifts, specifically strengthened ACC and hippocampus/amygdala and inter-amygdala coupling, and reduced amygdala-thalamus coupling within-group.

Moreover, a cross-sectional case–control neurophysiology study among 69 female participants (35 with chronic insomnia disorder and 34 healthy controls) with resting-state EEG, aiming to identify EEG-based connectivity alterations in chronic insomnia disorder and test whether macroscale global brain connectivity differences align with emotion-related cognition and cortical neurotransmitter distributions (24). Additionally, Yu et al. evaluated whether global brain connectivity features separate chronic insomnia disorder from healthy controls. Women with chronic insomnia exhibited increased EEG global connectivity, particularly in gamma-band coupling within the medial prefrontal and limbic cortices, compared to healthy sleepers. Cognitive decoding linked the abnormal connectivity patterns to issues in ER and mental control, indicating a dysregulated integration between top-down processes and the limbic system in chronic insomnia disorder. Spatial regression analysis connected these macroscale patterns to the distributions of norepinephrine, dopamine, and serotonin receptors and transporters, suggesting that neuromodulatory influences affect arousal and emotional states. Although correlations with insomnia severity were minimal and uncorrected, the clinical significance of the brain coupling remains uncertain. The study highlights EEG-based global connectivity as a cost-effective biomarker for chronic insomnia disorder and suggests neurochemical pathways for developing mechanism-informed treatments.

Research using fMRI and EEG indicates that insomnia is linked to overactive ER networks at rest. An fMRI study showed hyperconnectivity between the thalamo-limbic area, the ACC, and the prefrontal cortex, which improved with acupuncture treatment alongside sleep and mood improvements. An EEG study in women with chronic insomnia also identified gamma-band hyperconnectivity between the medial prefrontal cortex and the limbic system, aligning with ER and monoaminergic receptor maps. These findings point to dysregulation in the ER network, suggesting potential treatment targets and low-cost biomarkers, despite limitations of cross-sectional studies.

3.4. Interventions that target or influence ER in insomnia

3.4.1. ER-enhanced behavioural interventions

Three studies investigated whether adding ER components (e.g., acceptance, rumination reduction, inhibitory-control training) to insomnia care improves sleep and affect beyond sleep-mechanics alone (25 - 27). This section reviews studies that embed ER modules as part of an intervention and track ER-relevant outcomes.

Firstly, one of the studies (reference), a cross-sectional observational study previously synthesised in the “Emotion-regulation disturbances observed in insomnia” section, emphasised that diminished cognitive inhibition predicted insomnia-specific rumination. In contrast, set-shifting was unrelated (20). Moreover, one study asserted that response-inhibition deficits were phenotype-specific and potentially trainable (25). They recruited 22 healthy controls and 81 patients with insomnia disorder, who were further categorised into two groups - insomnia with short sleep duration (ISSD) and insomnia with normal sleep duration (INSD). Their two-phase, randomised double-blind trial consisted of conducting a cross-sectional comparison of inhibitory control across individuals with ISSD, INSD and healthy controls. Secondly, the researchers randomly allocated the individuals within each ID phenotype into separate groups, along with the healthy control group: those who underwent the inhibition-control training and a control group within each phenotype. The two training subgroups engaged in the Adaptive Go/NoGo training task 15 times within three weeks. The task focuses on training participants in inhibitory control through an adaptive difficulty adjustment, and all participants were evaluated using a range of subjective sleep-related assessments and objective sleep characteristics assessed by all-night sleep EEG. In the ISSD group, training focused on inhibitory control enhanced both inhibition and perceived sleep quality. Conversely, the INSD group showed general improvements over time without benefiting from the training, which suggests a cognitive-emotional arousal profile rather than difficulties with inhibitory control. Additionally, cross-sectional relationships emphasised this difference: in the

ISSD group, improved sleep was linked to better inhibition, while in the INSD group, cognitive arousal was associated with subjective sleep quality and duration. Mechanistically, the findings suggest impaired response inhibition characterises ISSD but not INSD, aligning with a phenotype in which short objective sleep coincides with executive dysfunction and that the cortical inhibition deficits sustain ISSD and are trainable. At the same time, INSD may benefit more from cognitive-affective targets than inhibition drills.

Secondly, a parallel-group RCT aimed to test whether acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT) improves subjective sleep, experiential avoidance and ER deficits in chronic insomnia beyond nonspecific group contact (26). They have recruited 35 participants with DSM-5 insomnia from an Iranian university sleep clinic and randomly allocated them into one of two conditions: a condition where participants underwent an ACT protocol (17 participants) and a condition where participants took part in an active social-support group (18 participants). Participants were assessed by self-rating questionnaires on sleep quality, dysfunctional beliefs and attitudes about sleep, ER, acceptance of sleep problems and experiential avoidance at baseline, eight weeks post-treatment, and follow-up after 12 weeks. Participants in the intervention condition also kept a weekly sleep log for eight consecutive weeks, consisting of information regarding subjective sleep duration, sleep quality, and the feeling of being restored. The results show that the participants in the intervention group recorded improved sleep duration (increase by approximately two hours) and a significant decrease in sleep quality and dysfunctional beliefs scores, with substantial improvements in ER and experiential avoidance scores, with enhancements being stable until follow-up. In contrast, active-control participants showed little to no change, further underscoring the ACT-specific effects. The sleep log micro-analysis also showed that these improvements occurred within the first three weeks of treatment. These findings suggest that ACT potentially breaks the insomnia–dysregulation loop by teaching acceptance and values-guided action and highlight experiential avoidance reduction as a driver of parallel improvements in sleep and ER, positioning ACT as an effective adjunct or alternative when CBT-I alone proves insufficient.

Thirdly, a parallel-group randomised waitlist-controlled trial testing a hybrid digital CBT-I + Emotion Regulation (dCBT-I+ER) programme versus waitlist in employed adults aimed to evaluate whether workplace-delivered dCBT-I+ER improves insomnia and affective symptoms (depression, anxiety), with secondary impacts on well-being, quality of life, productivity, and subjective/objective sleep parameters (27). Moukhtarian et al. have recruited 159 employees (79 in the intervention group; 80 in the waitlist control group) and assessed participants using a sleep diary and actigraphy along with subjective measures for insomnia, depression, anxiety, work productivity, job satisfaction, well-being and quality of life. Moreover, although not explicitly administering any ER measures, the ER component was an explicit intervention component. Their findings show that the intervention group showed significant improvements in insomnia, well-being, depression and anxiety, with sleep diary data supporting these results; however, actigraphy did not show clear between-group gains. Subsequently, work productivity, job satisfaction and quality of life did not yield significant changes. These findings suggest that the dCBT-I+ER achieves mental-health benefits (insomnia, depression, anxiety) on par with or exceeding typical digital mood interventions.

Integrating ER components into insomnia treatments has shown benefits beyond addressing sleep mechanics. For example, inhibitory control training improved both inhibition and subjective sleep in individuals with short sleep duration. The ACT effectively reduced dysfunctional beliefs and experiential avoidance while enhancing sleep quality. A hybrid program combining CBT-I with ER components also led to significant improvements in insomnia, depression, and anxiety. These findings indicate that ER-enhanced interventions can alleviate emotional burdens and improve perceived sleep. However, objective sleep improvements were inconsistent, and some studies lacked direct measurement of ER, indicating a need for mechanism-checked, longer follow-up RCTs focused on specific sleep phenotypes.

3.4.2. Standard insomnia therapies – ER outcomes

Here, we examine three studies examining whether treatments designed primarily for sleep, including acupuncture and most notably cognitive behavioural therapy for insomnia (CBT-I) and its digital variants, also change ER-adjacent states such as negative affect, hyperarousal, worry, and global ER difficulty, even when ER is not an explicit treatment target (23, 28, 29)

Firstly, as previously mentioned, experimental evidence suggests that, unlike in good sleepers, a night of sleep in insomnia can intensify next-day somatic distress after emotional exposure (22). These position affect load and perseverative cognition as modifiable targets for treatment. A study conducted by Tamm et al. investigated this phenomenon by asking whether digital CBT-I alters emotion processing and adjoining states, and whether those changes help lift depression in people with insomnia (28). In a randomised, single-blind trial among 205 adults (with 101 in the digital CBT-I vs 104 participants in the sleep-hygiene education group) with DSM-5 insomnia and clinically significant depressive symptoms were assessed at 5 and 10 weeks on sleep, depression, positive and negative affect, ER difficulties, and worry. A coprimary Facial Emotion Recognition Task (FERT) probed perceptual bias. CBT-I produced considerable improvements in insomnia and depression, plus shifts in affect (increased positive affect and decreased negative affect), a decrease in ER difficulties, and a decrease in worry. Additionally, early reductions (week-5) in negative affect, worry, and ER difficulty mediated ~22–30% of the week-10 depression benefit, whereas FERT bias did not change. Therefore, these findings suggest CBT-I seems to help by down-shifting state negative affect and repetitive negative thinking, not by improving facial-emotion accuracy. This mechanism is consistent with previous findings of Wassing et al. (22), suggesting that reducing the reactive/ruminative load going into the night and sleep no longer propagates distress into the following day.

Moreover, a randomised pilot parallel-arm trial investigated 56 binge-drinking adults with DSM-5 insomnia, with 28 participants in the CBT-I group and 28 in the control group (29). The aim was to determine whether CBT-I could improve four proposed mediators of the insomnia-alcohol link: alcohol craving, delay discounting, negative affect, and difficulties in ER, beyond the effects of sleep hygiene alone. The study implemented a five-session CBT-I treatment compared to a single-session sleep hygiene control. Results showed that CBT-I resulted in modest reductions in alcohol craving at post-treatment, with this effect partially mediated by improvements in insomnia. After one month, CBT-I also decreased delay discounting for larger rewards, indicating a better evaluation of long-term outcomes. However, the two groups had no significant change in negative affect. Additionally, while there was a substantial decrease in difficulties with ER within the CBT-I group, this finding did not hold up after correcting for baseline imbalances. In summary, standard sleep therapy can positively influence targets related to ER, specifically alcohol craving and impulsive decision-making, primarily through improvements in sleep. However, broader mood and ER measures may require longer treatment durations or targeted modules focused on ER.

Lastly, in addition to the findings of the aforementioned study exploring whether acupuncture modulates the EN rsFC, real acupuncture outperformed sham on sleep quality, anxiety, depression and hyperarousal (23). There was also a modest improvement in actigraphic SE, although total sleep time (TST) changes were minimal. Since no specific ER instrument was utilised, the findings should be regarded as related to ER outcomes, with reductions in negative emotions and hyperarousal potentially linked to enhanced ER. The imaging results indicate that acupuncture may improve the coupling between the cingulate and limbic systems, leading to better integration of the anterior cingulate with the amygdala and hippocampus, while decreasing coupling between the thalamus and amygdala. This may be one way acupuncture improves mood and hyperarousal and enhances sleep quality. However, it is essential to note that the brain-symptom correlations observed were only at a trend level after adjustments for multiple comparisons, suggesting that functional connectivity should be considered a plausible, though not definitively proven, mediator. Overall, acupuncture reduces emotional distress and hyperarousal while improving SE, with the underlying network-level emotional regulation mechanisms inferred, rather than directly measured.

In three trials, insomnia therapies improved sleep and emotional regulation. Digital CBT-I reduced insomnia and depression, leading to early decreases in negative emotions and worry, which later improved mood, though facial-emotion bias remained unchanged. A brief CBT-I for young adult drinkers

reduced alcohol cravings and impulsive decisions mainly through better sleep, while broader mood effects were limited. Acupuncture improved sleep quality, anxiety, and depression, showing links to brain activity. Overall, sleep-focused treatments reduced emotional distress, but objective sleep changes were mixed, indicating a need for longer-term studies to explore the underlying mechanisms.

3.4.3. ER as a predictor/moderator of treatment response

Finally, we discuss two studies exploring whether baseline ER traits and strategies (e.g., catastrophising, rumination, refocus-on-planning) and clinical context (psychiatric comorbidity) predict or moderate insomnia-treatment outcomes, to identify ER-informed risk stratification and augmentation pathways for CBT-I (30, 31).

Firstly, a cross-sectional case-control comparison aimed to clarify which cognitive-emotional factors best explain objectively measured sleep onset latency, SE and TST in young adults (30). In 40 young adults (20 young adults with DSM-5 insomnia vs 20 age-matched healthy sleepers) tracked with 10-day actigraphy, maladaptive emotion-focused coping and dysfunctional sleep beliefs uniquely predicted worse objective sleep in the insomnia group, even after anxiety, depression, arousal predisposition and sleep-reactivity were considered. These findings suggest that individuals high on emotion-focused coping and sleep-related beliefs may show diminished response to treatment of insomnia, placing coping and dysfunctional beliefs as potential moderators of CBT-I response.

Secondly, van de Laar et al. have investigated whether DSM-IV psychiatric comorbidity and cognitive ER styles predicted poor CBT-I outcomes and affected the treatment effect (31). Their longitudinal uncontrolled case series study recruited 60 participants. Thirty of those participants had a comorbid psychiatric disorder, such as major depressive disorder, dysthymic disorder, bipolar disorder, panic disorder, generalised anxiety disorder, social anxiety disorder, undifferentiated somatoform disorder, adaptation disorder and ADHD. In contrast, the other 30 had no psychiatric comorbidity. After completing an eight-session CBT-I protocol, results indicate that psychiatric comorbidity was the most notable driver of remission odds (indicated by ISI scores < 8 after CBT-I), with 83% patients without comorbidity achieving remission compared to only 23% of patients with comorbidity. Additionally, while considering mood symptoms and personality traits, the forward multivariate logistic analysis results show that one CERQ facet - refocus-on-planning - independently worsened the odds of remission. Subsequently, comorbidity and overplanning classify most non-responders. At the same time, other maladaptive strategies (such as rumination and catastrophising) showed no independent effect, implying that psychiatric comorbidities, unaddressed mental health disorders and excessive planning negatively predict CBT-I outcomes, outweighing other personality and coping traits.

Two studies indicate that baseline ER style and clinical context can predict the effectiveness of insomnia treatment. In young adults, emotion-based coping and dysfunctional beliefs about sleep are associated with poorer sleep outcomes, suggesting they may hinder CBT-I effectiveness. A clinical case series highlighted psychiatric comorbidity as a key predictor of non-remission after CBT-I. In contrast, a focus on planning domain correlated with worse results. These findings emphasise the need for pre-treatment stratification, including assessment of comorbidity, coping strategies, and sleep-related beliefs, to better tailor treatments like combining CBT-I with ER-focused interventions and providing necessary psychiatric care.

4. Limitations of current research and potential directions for future research

Current evidence suggests a link between ER and insomnia; however, several limitations hinder causal inference and translation. Firstly, much of the existing literature relies on cross-sectional designs and short trial follow-up periods. Even in randomised studies, many utilise passive or poorly matched controls, making it challenging to isolate ER-specific mechanisms. Secondly, there is substantial measurement heterogeneity: ER is assessed using various methods, including global difficulty ratings, specific strategies, negative reactivity states, or manipulated without proper measurement. Sleep is often self-reported, with fewer studies employing actigraphy or multi-night polysomnography (PSG).

To address these gaps, future research should focus on several key areas. Firstly, RCTs designed to explore underlying mechanisms with active, contact-matched controls and more extended follow-up periods are needed to establish temporal precedence. Additionally, studies should implement a

standardised ER assessment battery, physiological measures (e.g., heart rate variability) and multi-night PSG/actigraphy to quantify subjective-objective discrepancies. Moreover, future studies should adopt multimodal designs (e.g., EEG/fMRI) to link changes in neural circuits, such as cingulo-limbic connectivity, to ER states and clinical outcomes. Finally, it is essential to broaden the diversity and ecological context of research by including older adults, men, underrepresented groups, and settings like workplaces and primary care, to enhance the generalizability of findings.

5. Conflict of interest

The author of this paper declares that he has no conflict of interest in the topic, development and publication of this paper and that the development and publication of this paper were not supported by any pharmaceutical company. This declaration also applies to all co-authors.

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